

JOB STRESS OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN RELATION TO THEIR ATTITUDE TOWARDS TEACHING PROFESSION

Hetal Patel

Research Scholar

University Of Mumbai

Research Guide : Dr. Frances Vaidya

Abstract

Teaching is an application of knowledge, skills and attributes designed to provide unique service to meet the educational needs of the students. With changing current situations in teaching field, teachers are experiencing job stress. The study aimed at finding out the relationship between job stress and attitude towards teaching profession among secondary school teachers on the basis of gender and types of school board. Methodology used was descriptive type (Survey). Job stress and Attitude towards teaching profession scale was constructed by the researcher. The sample size consists of 610 secondary school teachers. Data was descriptively and inferentially analysed. For the analysis Pearson's coefficient correlation test was used to find out relationship between job stress and attitude towards teaching profession. It revealed that there is no relationship between Job stress and Attitude towards teaching profession on the basis of gender and types of school board.

Key words: *Job stress, Attitude towards teaching profession, ICSE and SSC secondary school teachers, Female and Male Teachers*

1. Introduction

Last 10 years are considered as whirlwind for the teaching profession due to new technology. The policy are changing like a pendulum that swung back and forth, and there has been a growing number of demands put on teachers' part. There's an increasing amount of responsibility and accountability for teachers. To maintain high standard of education quality there are chances teachers experience job stress in order to adjust and cope up with new challenges. While managing job stress there are chances

that attitude towards teaching profession may get affected.

1.1 Job Stress

Stress is derived from the Latin word ‘**stringere**’ which means to be drawn tight. Stress is defined as a dynamic condition in which an individual is confronted with an opportunity, constraint, or demand related to what he or she desires and for which the outcome is perceived to be uncertain and important. is a chronic disease caused by conditions in the workplace that negatively affect an individual performance and overall wellbeing of his body and mind. (Robbins,2001) One or more of a host of physical and mental illness manifests job stress. Stress at work is a phenomenon of modern lifestyles. Job stress is a problem in almost all the countries of the world, irrespective of whether the economy is strong or weak. In most of the cases, stress leads to reduced efficiency in even the best of the individuals, which in turn leads to reduced productivity.

1.2 Attitude Towards Teaching Profession

Attitude is defined as a state of readiness shaped through the experience and influences the response of individual towards the stimuli. – (Freemen,1985). Attitude is the most important area of psychological measurement. To describes anyone personality, one of its main expressions is attitude, which an individual has towards other persons, activities and institutions. It is precursor of the behaviour and varies from favourable to unfavourable conditions. Attitude is made up of three components affective, behavioural and cognitive hence acts as a yardstick of the individual behaviour (Feldman, 1985)

1.3 Review Of Related Literature

Dhar and Magotra (2018) ‘Compared Occupational Stress Among Teachers Teaching in JKBOSE & CBSE in Jammu District’ revealed that teachers from JKBOSE and CBSE differ significantly on various stress-related areas such as role over-load, role ambiguity, role conflict, group and political pressures responsibility for persons, under-participation, powerlessness and poor peer relations.

Harmesen, Helms, Maulana and Veen (2018) examined ‘The relationship between beginning teachers’ stress causes, stress responses, teaching behaviour and attrition. indicates that teachers experienced negative pupil behaviour are directly related to tension, negative emotions and discontent among teachers. Relationships with pupils are the basic thing for teachers, if efforts are made to improve this

relationship then teacher stress, attrition and the negative effect of stress can be control.

Sharma (2016) studied the **Attitude of Pupil-Teachers towards Teaching Profession in Relation to Gender and Background**. Finding suggests that majority of teachers had a positive attitude towards the teaching profession. There existed no significant difference in the attitude of male and female teachers towards teaching profession. There existed no significant difference in the attitude of rural and urban teachers towards teaching profession.

Egwu (2015) studied **Attitude of teachers towards Teaching Profession in Nigeria: Implications for Education Development**. Results showed that a lot of factors have contributed to the negative attitude of teachers towards teaching profession among them are the low salary, irregular payment of salaries and fringe benefit, lack of promotion, excess work load, poor environment, parent negative influence and poor financing of education etc.

1.4 Aim Of The Study

To find out relationship between job stress and attitude towards teaching profession of secondary school teachers.

1.5 Objectives Of The Study

- To ascertain the relationship between job stress and attitude towards teaching profession of female secondary school teachers.
- To ascertain the relationship between job stress and attitude towards teaching profession of male secondary school teachers.
- To ascertain the relationship between job stress and attitude towards teaching profession of SSC board secondary school teachers.
- To ascertain the relationship between job stress and attitude towards teaching profession of ICSE secondary school teachers.

1.6 Hypothesis Of The Study

- There is no significant relationship between job stress and attitude towards teaching profession of female secondary school teachers.
- There is no significant relationship between job stress and attitude towards teaching profession of male secondary school teachers.
- There is no significant relationship between job stress and attitude towards teaching profession of SSC board secondary school teachers.

- There is no significant relationship between job stress and attitude towards teaching profession of ICSE board secondary school teachers.

2. Research Methodology

2.1 Methodology Of The Study: The study is of the quantitative descriptive type. It is also correlational type because it deals with the present status of job stress of secondary school teachers with relation to their attitude towards teaching profession.

2.2. Sampling: The sample consisted of teachers from 49 SSC board schools and 34 ICSE board schools of Greater Mumbai, where the medium of instruction is English. The total sample consisted of 610 secondary school teachers. 361 SSC board and 249 ICSE board secondary school teachers .498 female teachers and 112 male teachers. Sampling was done into three stage where in first stage schools were selected through stratified sampling and in second stage schools were selected on basis of SSC and ICSE board and in third stage teacher's data were collected by random sampling.

2.3 Tool Used: Job stress and Attitude towards teaching profession tools were constructed by researcher and its reliability is 0.781 and 0.839 by Split Half method.

2.4 Data Analysis: Data collected for the main study was analysed by Pearson's coefficient of correlation test to find out relationship between two variables.

3. Result

For hypothesis 1. There is no significant relationship between job stress and attitude towards teaching profession. of female secondary school teachers.

Table no.1: Job stress and Attitude towards teaching profession of female secondary school teachers.

Sample size	Df	'r'	los	Result
498	496	0.111	Not Significant	Hypothesis accepted

Interpretation of 'r': The coefficient of correlation between job stress and attitude towards teaching profession of female secondary school teachers is 0.111, which is positive, shows very negligible relationship and not significant at 0.01 level. Hence null hypothesis is accepted.

Conclusion: There is a no relationship between job stress and attitude towards teaching profession of female secondary school teachers.

Discussion: Job stress of female secondary school teachers and attitude towards teaching profession has no correlation and shows no dependency on each other. Job stress and attitude towards teaching profession are two independent criteria which do not influence and over shadow each other. The probable reason is that female teachers believe in work ethics and do not compromise on it for the student's better education.

For hypothesis 2. There is no significant relationship between job stress and attitude towards teaching profession of male secondary school teachers.

Table no.2: Job stress and Attitude towards teaching profession. of male secondary school teachers.

Sample size	Df	'r'	l.o.s	Result
112	110	0.197	Not significant	Hypothesis accepted

Interpretation of 'r': The coefficient of correlation between job stress and attitude towards teaching profession of male secondary school teachers is 0.197, which is positive, shows very negligible relationship and not significant at 0.01 level. Hence null hypothesis is accepted.

Conclusion: There is no relationship between job stress and attitude towards teaching profession of male secondary school teachers.

Discussion: Job stress of male secondary school teachers and attitude towards teaching profession has no correlation and shows no dependency on each other. Male teachers are mostly less emotional and more practical. They have better hold on student's discipline. But still, they also face job stress due to constant change in teaching profession. But still, they keep their attitude towards teaching on higher side for betterment of students.

For hypothesis 3. There is no significant relationship between job stress and attitude towards teaching profession. of SSC board secondary school teachers.

Table no.3: Job stress and Attitude towards teaching profession. of SSC board secondary school teachers.

Sample size	Df	'r'	l.o.s	Result
361	359	0.110	Not Significant	Hypothesis accepted

Interpretation of 'r': The coefficient of correlation between job stress and attitude towards teaching profession of SSC board secondary school teachers is 0.110, which is positive, shows very negligible relationship and not significant at 0.01 level. Hence null hypothesis is accepted.

Conclusion: There is no relationship between job stress and attitude towards teaching profession of SSC board secondary school teachers.

Discussion: Job stress of SSC board secondary school teachers and attitude towards teaching profession has no correlation and shows no dependency on each other. Due to job stress, there is reduction in work performance and output, inability to manage time, feeling alienation, loss of confidence and motivation and poor peer relation. But teachers face all the mention problem still they fight and wants to give best to students by keeping high attitude towards teaching profession.

For hypothesis 4. There is no significant relationship between job stress and attitude towards teaching profession. of ICSE board secondary school teachers.

Table no.4: Job stress and Attitude towards teaching profession of ICSE board secondary school teachers.

Sample size	Df	'r'	<u>l.o.s</u>	Result
249	247	-0.078	Not Significant	Hypothesis accepted

Interpretation of 'r': The coefficient of correlation between job stress and attitude towards teaching profession of ICSE board secondary school teachers is -0.078, which is positive, shows very negligible relationship and not significant at 0.01 level. Hence null hypothesis is accepted.

Conclusion: There is no relationship between job stress and attitude towards teaching profession of ICSE board secondary school teachers.

Discussion: Job stress of ICSE board secondary school teachers and attitude towards teaching profession has no correlation and shows no dependency on each other. Teachers today are continually charged with new responsibilities as a response to the changing world outside the school. Changes in the society at large require corresponding changes within the school if the latter is to be responsive to society's ever-changing needs. To the extent that stress experienced by teachers affects professional performance. But still practical in approach teachers attitude remains very high to give best to their student.

4. Conclusion

There is no relationship between job stress and attitude towards teaching profession with respect to female secondary school teacher, male secondary school teacher, SSC board secondary school teacher and ICSE board secondary school teacher. Thus it can be said that job stress and attitude towards teaching profession are both independent variables and do not have any impact and influence on each other.

5. Suggestions

SUGGESTION TO REDUCE JOB STRESS OF TEACHERS.

Work out priorities, identify your stress situations in school, don't react to imagined insults, think before you commit to any school work, move on if you made any mistake, don't dwell on past mistakes, help students to cope with stress, think positively, ask for help from your school members and make a connection with colleague

SUGGESTION TO IMPROVE TEACHERS ATTITUDE TOWARDS TEACHING PROFESSION

To developing a positive attitude, **stop complaining about things which cannot be control by you, Use a positive vocabulary, Practice gratitude towards your work, Keep visual reminders, Interact with positive people**, Surround yourself with positive people, Control your language when talking to students, and always give priority to your professionalism and work ethos.

References:

- Ali,M.(2014). A study of the organizational climate of college of education in relation to the job value and attitude towards teaching profession. Unpublished Doctoral Dissertation. University of Mumbai.
- Hastrup.T.(2013). Stress Among Secondary School Teachers in Ekiti State, Nigeria. Journal of Educational and Social Research. Vol .3, pp 311-317.
- Sharma.D.(2008). Occupational stress among teachers working in secondary schools of Karauli district of Rajasthan state. Unpublished Doctoral Dissertation. Kerala University
- Ghosh, S. and Bairgya, S. (2010). Attitude of secondary school teachers towards teaching profession in relation to some demographic variables, Edusearch Vol 1(1), pp 55-58.